

A journal of new and advance biology

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The aim of *The Applied Biology & Chemistry Journal (TAB CJ)* is to be a focus for communication in research on the application of biological, biomedical and chemical sciences for studying, analyzing and understanding biological problems. Although the primary purpose of *TAB CJ* is to offer a journal where cutting-edge research of broad interest may be published rapidly, without compromising on the quality, the additional features including avant-garde reviews will extend the scope of the journal by continuing its role beyond the reporting of research results.

The best account of the topics covered in *TAB CJ* is to say that they encompass the application of the multidisciplinary approach in investigating biological problems. It is characterised by a sagacity of academic eagerness inspired by what may coarsely define it as the panorama of illuminating the arrangements in the authority of their application in biological and biomedical sciences. Such research has its roots in quite a lot of traditional disciplines. Until now, in the milieu of recent research on the application of biology and biomedical science in studying and analysing the biological problems, these punitive divisions have arisen to describe further the techniques used more than the notions upon which the study rests. *TAB CJ* thus purposes to offer a single journal to publish research establishing part of this gestalt but originating in anyone of many experimental approaches.

A large proportion of the papers published in *TAB CJ* will be the product of trailblazing research, which in a sense, will bridge the gap between classical biology of the past with the advent of modern biology in a multi-dimensional aspect. But *TAB CJ* will not solely be a

journal of research findings in applied biology but also will impart both interesting techniques and novel methods from the viewpoint of addressing the biological issues of the third world population to which the scientific discoveries are inaccessible, will represent an essential part of the journal. Experiments in areas defined by the traditional terms, for instance, developmental genetics, immunology, pathology, virology or studies based on clinical trials of newer treatments or vaccines, also contribute to the present framework of multidisciplinary prospects in biological science.

The manuscripts will be accepted chiefly based on their novelty, principle, methodology and applications. *TAB CJ* will stand-out with a publication policy that cartels the selection for the vast interest and significance with a devotion to serving authors, guaranteeing high standard and productive editorial and peer-reviewing process. Moreover, the performance of associated editors will considerably contribute to maintaining the journal's quality and reputation by ensuring that the high-quality work submitted to the journal for publication is reviewed by the experts in their respective fields. With the aim to reach the vast audience, an association with various global indexing and database managing agencies will be considered soon. The journal will follow the strict double-blind peer-review process for making the reviewing unbiased and will comply with the ethical practices of publishing. *TAB CJ* comply with the 'zero-tolerance policy' towards plagiarism if found at any point of time making the manuscript ineligible for consideration in the journal and likely be rejected. In no circumstances, *TAB CJ* will compromise with the publication standards and ethics.

Rapid publication is essentially necessary aim of this journal; its determination to make papers accessible as quickly as is unswerving with proper reviewing and sound reproduction of the manuscripts. Accepted papers will take about less than a month to publish; of course, an author with a document to communicate for foremost publication will be eligible for a swift decision on its acceptability for the journal. It will, therefore, be the aim of *TAB CJ* to provide the authors with critical and peer-reviewed comments and suggestions on their manuscript from the referees and decisions by the editorial board within two to three weeks after submission. In order to offer speedy publication, it will also be taken care that the publication ethics are not compromised. Any delays accounted during the publication time due to peer-reviewing and revision process shall be minimized but allowing *TAB CJ* to draw upon the expertise of global researchers for the quality of the article, thereof, shall be of high priority. Even though the associate and executive editors of this

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journal will evaluate various submitted papers, it would become unrealistic for them to consider all submissions, and *TABCJ* will, therefore, request other researchers to review the manuscripts falling in their area of expertise.

Contributions to biology are made not only by reporting research but also by reviews, opinions and editorials. *TABCJ* will again endure representing these features in its issues. Since writing an original research article essentially has limited readers, it may pose difficulty for the researchers to persist abundant and up-to-date knowledge of the work which, though feasibly not of instantaneous significance for their research, may, however, be useful. Lengthier reviews will fulfill the customary drive of comprehensive discussion over a topic in-depth but will lack the constraints which must go together with the presentation of original research outcomes. Generally, mini-reviews of about four to six pages will present the complementary objective of discussing in concrete terms, the recent developments in some subject, mainly for the profit of researchers in interrelated issues. By discussing in all the topics on which *TABCJ* publishes original articles, these short reviews will try to benefit readers of the journal to follow research over an extensive spectrum of biology.

Any interpretation of the subjects on which *TABCJ* will publish research can only be imprecise, since the emphasis of our instantaneous attention shifts with time, and as therefore, will the contents of the journal. Of late, its foundation in 2020, when the entire world has been dealing with the substantial turmoil that is being caused by an unprecedented status quo of the COVID-19 contagion, *TABCJ* proffers a platform for research work aimed toward a multi-dimensional perspective to finding panacea to global problems. Besides COVID-19 pandemic, quite a few other issues, including crop yield, alternative non-carbon fuel, multiple drug resistance in pathogens, alternative therapeutics, public health, waste management and environmental pollution, have important impacts in the developing world and newly industrialized countries. The journal chiefly reports on advances for and from evolving expanses. By publishing articles of all purposes and not merely of a specialist curiosity in all of the areas accounting to our contemporary opinion of the maneuver of the *TABCJ*, and by including in the same issues of the journal, review articles endeavoring to help scientists to follow an extensive array of topics, *The Applied Biology & Chemistry Journal* hopes to turn out to be in essence a journal of new and advance biology.